

FUNKSIYANING KESMADAGI ENG KATTA VA ENG KICHIK QIYMATI.

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ANNOTATSIYA.

Funksiya hosilalari yordamida eng katta eng kichikga tekshirish yo’llari ta’rif teoremlari ushbu maqolada ko’rsatilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: Qiymat, differensiallash, uzluksiz, chegara.

Avval ekstremumning zaruriy shartini ifodalovchi teoremani keltiramiz. Kesmaning ichki nuqtalarida differensiallanuvchi va kesma chegaralarida uzluksiz bo’lgan funksiyaning kesmadagi eng katta va eng kichik qiymatlarini topish quyidagicha bajariladi:

1. Funksiya hosilasini nolga tenglashtirib, kesmaning ichki sohasiga tegishli bo’lgan kritik nuqtalar topiladi.
2. Funksiyaning kesmaning chegaraviy nuqtalaridagi qiymatlari va kesma ichiga tegishli bo’lgan kritik nuqtalardagi qiymatlari hisoblanadi.
3. Funksiyaning topilgan qiymatlari o’zaro taqqoslanib, ulardan eng kichik va eng kattasi aniqlanadi.

Eslatma. Yopiq oraliqda aniqlangan va uzluksiz bo’lgan funksiyaning shu kesmadagi eng kichik va eng katta qiymatlarini topish quyidagi teoreмага asoslanadi.

Veyershtrass teoremasi. $[a; b]$ kesmada aniqlangan va uzluksiz bo’lgan $f(x)$ funksiya shu kesmada o’zining eng kichik va eng katta qiymatini qabul qiladi.

1 - teorema . Agar $x = x_0$ nuqtada $f(x)$ funksiyaning hosilasi nolga teng bo’lib, x_0 nuqtadan o’tishda o’z ishoracini o’zgartirsa, x_0 ekstremum nuqtasi bo’ladi.

- 1) Agar bunda hosilaning ishorasi musbatdan manfiyga o’zgarsa, maksimum nuqtasi bo’ladi.
- 2) Agar bunda hosilaning ishorasi manfiydan musbatga o’zgarsa, x_0 minimum nuqtasi bo’ladi.

Isbot. Teorema shartiga ko’ra $f'(x_0)=0$, $f'(x_1)>0$, $f'(x_2)<0$, $x_1<x_0<x_2$, x_1 va x_2 nuqtalar x_0 nuqtaga yetarlicha yaqin nuqtalar. Faraz qilaylik, hosila o’z ishorasini musbatdan manfiyga o’zgartirsin, ya’ni $f'(x_1)>0$, $x_0-\varepsilon < x < x_0$ va $f'(x_2)<0$, $x_0 < x_2 < x_0 + \varepsilon$ bo’lsin. Bu tengsizliklardan $(x_0-\varepsilon; x_0)$ intervalda funksiya o’suvchi, ya’ni

$f(x) < f(x_0)$ va $(x_0; x_0 + \varepsilon + \varepsilon)$ intervalda esa funksiya kamayuvchi, ya'ni $f(x) > f(x_0)$ bo'lishi kelib chiqadi. Shunday qilib, har qanday $x \in (x_0 - \varepsilon; x_0 + \varepsilon)$ uchun $f(x) < f(x_0)$ tengsizlik bajariladi.

Demak, $f(x_0)$ funksiya maksimumi, x_0 esa maksimum nuqtasidir. Teoremaning ikkinchi qismi ham shunga o'xshash isbotlanadi.

1-misol. $f(x) = x^3 - 3x$ funksiyaning ekstremumlarini toping.

Yechish. $f'(x) = 3x^2 - 3 = 3(x+1)(x-1)$ hosila $x_1 = -1$; $x_2 = 1$ nuqtalarda nolga teng bo'ladi. $x < -1$ va $f'(x) > 0$ va $-1 < x < 1$ da $f'(x) < 0$ bo'lgani uchun $x_1 = -1$ — maksimum nuqtasi; $-1 < x < 1$ da $f'(x) < 0$ va $x > 1$ da $f'(x) > 0$ bo'lgani uchun $x_2 = 1$ — minimum nuqtasi bo'ladi.

$$f_{\min} = f(1) = 1^3 - 3 \cdot 1 = -2; f_{\max} = f(-1) = -1 + 3 = 2$$

Misol: $y = x^3 + 3x^2 - 9x + 1$ funksiyaning [2,5]

[2,5] kesmadagi eng katta va eng kichik qiymatlarini aniqlang.

Yechish:

a) Kritik nuqtalarni topamiz : y funksiya uchun hosilani hisoblaymiz:
 $y' = 3x^2 + 6x - 9$ $y' = 0$ tenglamani yechamiz:

$$3x^2 + 6x - 9 = 0 \quad x_1 = 1 \quad x_2 = -3$$

$$3x^2 + 6x - 9 = 0 \quad x_1 = 1 \quad x_2 = -3$$

Berilgan kesmaga faqat $x_1 = 1$ nuqta kiradi.

b) Funksiyaning $x = 1$ $x = -2$ $x = 5$ nuqtadagi qiymatlarni hisoblaymiz: $f(1) = -4$ $f(-2) = 23$ $f(5) = 156$
 $f(1) = -4$ $f(-2) = 23$ $f(5) = 156$

c) Topilgan qiymatlardan eng katta M ni va eng kichik m ni tanlaymiz.

$$M = f(5) = 156 \quad M = f(5) = 156 \quad \text{eng katta maksimum qiymat}$$

$$m = f(1) = -4 \quad x = 1 \quad \text{nuqtadagi eng kichik minimum qiymat.}$$

Misol: $y(x) = x^3 - 1,5x^2 - 6x + 1$

funksiyaning $[-2,0]$ kesmadagi eng katta va eng kichik qiymatlarni topamiz

$$\text{Oldin kritik nuqtalarni topamiz } y'(x) = 3x^2 - 3x - 6 \quad y'(x) = 0$$

$$y'(x) = 3x^2 - 3x - 6 \quad y'(x) = 0$$

$$3x^2 - 3x - 6 = 0 \quad x^2 - x - 2 = 0 \quad x_1 = -1 \quad x_2 = 2$$

$[-2,5][2,5]$ oraliqqa $x_1 = -1, x_2 = 2$ kritik nuqtalardagi qiymatlarini topamiz va bizga berilgan kesmadagi chetki nuqtalardagi qiymatlarni topish

$$y(-2) = -1$$

$$y(2) = 4.5$$

$$y(0) = 1$$

Eng kichik qiymati -2 nuqtada erishiladi va u -1 ga teng. Eng katta qiymat esa 2 nuqtada erishiladi va u 4.5 ga teng. Bu qisqacha bunday yoziladi:

$$\max_{[-2;2]} y(x) = y(2) = 4.5$$

$$\min_{[-2;2]} y(x) = y(-2) = -1$$

Misol. $y = \frac{x-1}{x+1}$ funksiyaning $[0;4]$ kesmadagi eng katta va eng kichik qiymatlarini toping.

Yechish. Funksiyani kritik nuqtasini topib olamiz.

$$y' = \frac{(x+1) - (x-1)}{(x+1)^2} = \frac{2}{(x+1)^2}$$

$y' > 0$ hech qachon nolga teng bo'lmaydi. Biz bilamizki funksiyani uzilish nuqtasi ham kritik nuqta bo'ladi. Demak $x = -1$ nuqta kritik nuqta ekan. Ammo bu nuqta bizga berilgan oraliqda yo'q. Shuning uchun berilgan kesmani chetki nuqtalardagi funksiya qiymatini topamiz va ularni solishtirib eng katta, eng kichik qiymatni topamiz.

$y(0) = -1$ $y(4) = 0,6$ Demak funksiyaning berilgan oraliqdagi eng katta qiymati $M = 0,6$ eng kichik qiymati esa $m = -1$ ekan.

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